

Challenges and Obstacles in Implementation of State Defense in University

Syan Rosyid Adiwinata¹, Dita Indra Febryanti², Respati Prajna Vasthi³

^{1,2,3} Industrial Electronics Study Program, Department of Electrical Engineering, Jakarta State Polytechnic

ABSTRACT: Based on The Fund for Place's survey regarding the global vulnerability index, data shows that Indonesia is currently ranked 99th out of 178 countries in the world. In this case, Indonesia will receive a warning as its predicate, and one day it may enter a high warning level. Indonesia's lower position in the global vulnerability index is none other than the result of the low participation of the younger generation in implementing state defense. This study aims to identify, process, and analyze data empirically regarding the challenges and obstacles to defending the state in higher education along with recommendations for solutions. This research uses a quantitative descriptive method, because this research will describe the current situation systematically and factually with the aim of analyzing data by describing or describing the data that has been collected as a solution to the research problem.

KEYWORDS: State Defense, Barriers, Implementation, Challenges

INTRODUCTION

In an era of increasingly sophisticated technology like now, it is able to bring about changes in every circle. These changes can be a blessing or vice versa, a threat to the younger generation who are not wise in using technology. Basically, fostering a sense of defending the country and having a sense of nationalism can be done through physical and non-physical activities. As long as the activities carried out are worth loving the motherland, aware of the nation and state and are willing to sacrifice. It is very important to remember that defending the country is not only the task of the TNI and POLRI, but the entire community, especially the younger generation in the digital era. Several countries also implement state defense through compulsory military service. In Indonesia, the constitutional basis for implementing state defense is outlined in Article 27 Paragraph 3 of the 1945 Constitution which reads "Every citizen has the right and obligation to participate in efforts to defend the state". In this case, the introduction of state defense is formulated directly and in depth, which includes implementation at the practical level. A sustainable program will have a real impact on people's lives. In line with the benefits obtained, of course there are challenges that must be faced such as geographical position as a strategic route in trade. The implementation of state defense at the student level is by forming a young generation who is disciplined and sensitive to the social environment. At present, it is indeed difficult for us to avoid technological developments, but it is not impossible for us to choose the use of technology according to our needs. The principle of benefits from technology is also more or less felt, but the negative impacts are no less numerous. Take social media as an example, in a research it was explained that 68.4% of respondents stated that social media had a negative impact on national security and could cause individuals to lose their sense of defending the country. However, as many as 31.6% of participants stated that they did not agree, because social media also had many positive impacts in advancing the nation and state of Indonesia. As for those who stated the negative impact of social media were changes in ideology, radicalism, drug trafficking, and the entry of foreign culture as much as 78.9%, then 15.8% of participants stated that the negative impact of social media was playing games, because games can reduce children's mentality and addicted to playing gadgets, and 5, 3% of participants said the impact of social media was not time discipline. [2]

The real threats to the identity of the nation's current generation are drugs, pornography, promiscuity, hoaxes, and radicalism/terrorism. The existence of violence and radicalism in the world of education today is that 84% of students have experienced violence at school and 75% of students admit that they have committed violence at school. This violence varies, there are physical and verbal bullying. The fatality was as many as 48.9% of students around Jabodetabek agreed to radical actions, this behavior was like a brawl between students. [3] With the many impacts that have been described from the use of technology, this illustrates the existence of challenges and obstacles in implementing state defense in universities.

This research was compiled based on 3 previous studies to describe the novelty of this study which shows the uniqueness and differences compared to previous studies. First, research from Suriata in 2019 with the title Actualization of State Defense Awareness for the Young Generation in Improving National Resilience. Second, research from Widiyanto and Istiqomah in 2019 with the title Fostering State Defense Awareness Through School Culture. Third, research from Hartono in 2020 with the title

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Phenomenon of State Defense Awareness in the Digital Age in the Perspective of National Resilience. These three studies are used as a reference for portraits of problems that occur related to the low awareness of state defense in society. This is a follow-up research, after finding the problems that occur, This study tries to analyze in depth the solutions to problems that occur in relation to the implementation of state defense in the younger generation. This study aims to identify challenges and obstacles in the implementation of state defense in higher education, especially vocational education programs, and how to overcome these problems.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This research uses a quantitative descriptive method, because this research will describe the current situation systematically and factually with the aim of analyzing data by describing or describing the data that has been collected as a solution to the research problem. The type of research carried out based on its type is included in case study research, so conclusions are drawn through analyzing questionnaires and interviews obtained from respondents. The objects of this research were 3rd and 5th semester students divided into 7 departments at the Jakarta State Polytechnic. Data collection techniques are carried out using:

a. questionnaire,

namely by using a structured list of questions submitted to respondents to obtain detailed answers including questions about gender in the experience of cheating, cheating for the first time, the role or position of the field of science in defending the country.

b. Interview.

Interviews were conducted to get a more detailed description of the object of research, and to help explain data analysis. Interviews were conducted with 3rd and 5th semester students of the Jakarta State Polytechnic. Data analysis in quantitative descriptive research can be carried out simultaneously with the process of collecting data and writing findings. Not all data collected needs to be included in the report, this can complicate the analysis process.

The analytical method used in this study is an interactive model by Miles & Huberman. The analysis is carried out continuously until the data is considered saturated. This analysis consists of data collection, data reduction, data presentation and drawing conclusions. The explanation for each of these stages is:

- 1) Data collection, data analysis can be carried out simultaneously with the process of collecting data and writing findings.
- 2) Data reduction, not all data obtained needs to be included in the report. The data is focused on the main findings according to the research theme. After reduction, the information provided from the data will be seen more clearly, so that it can be a reference for researchers to start analyzing or collecting further data to obtain additional data.
- 3) Presentation of data, data is presented based on the conclusions of the information that has been processed. Qualitative data is presented in narrative form which explains the relationship between information. This stage makes it easier for researchers to understand the actual field conditions and plan further work.
- 4) Conclusion. Conclusions can be made several times. Conclusions at the beginning of data collection are generally temporary because it is still possible to change given the amount of data and information being analyzed. However, if the initial conclusions have been supported by valid and consistent evidence according to field conditions, then these conclusions can be said to be final conclusions. Conclusions in qualitative research are new findings that never existed before.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Challenges in implementing state defense in tertiary institutions, especially in vocational education programs. Higher education as an institution consisting of intellectuals is urgently needed as the spearhead in the state defense implementation machine. Higher education as a center of excellence, a place to educate quality young people with high national spirit. For this reason, universities have an important role in advancing the national defense system through the implementation of state defense for students. Higher education institutions do not only act as motors for producing human resources who have the skills and knowledge needed by the industrial world, but also must be able to foster an attitude of nationalism in the younger generation and shape attitudes and behavior that are in accordance with the foundation of the Indonesian state, namely Pancasila. This is a form of mental revolution as well as to build the country's deterrence in facing the complex dynamics of threats that might occur. Based on the results of the questionnaire filled out by students of the Department of Electrical Engineering which can be seen in the graph below, regarding the application of the value of loving the homeland, it was found that 86% of students had implemented the values of loving the country, one of which was using domestic products rather than foreign products. . While 14% of them are still not aware of implementing these values of loving the motherland. That is, most of the students already have the awareness to implement the values of loving the motherland, but there are still a small number of them who still don't have that awareness. So, it is necessary to socialize Consciousness in the life of the nation and state is directed in the form of attitudes of behavior, socializing in accordance with the personality of the nation, always linking itself to the achievement of the ideals and goals of the life of the Indonesian people. Based on the results of a questionnaire regarding the implementation of nation and state awareness values, it was found that 95.5% of students had implemented nation and state awareness values, one of which was obeying traffic rules when driving to campus. While 4.5% of them still do not have awareness in implementing these conscious values of nation and state. That is, most of the students

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already have the awareness to implement the conscious values of being a nation-state, although it can be seen in the graph below that there are also a small number of them who still do not have this awareness. Thus, it is necessary to periodically socialize, monitor and evaluate to increase student awareness to implement the conscious values of nation and state.

The belief in Pancasila as the state's philosophy and ideology is the third state defense value. Pancasila as the philosophy and ideology of the nation and state is a framework of reference in the life of society, nation and state in order to achieve national goals. Based on the results of the questionnaire regarding the implementation of Pancasila Belief values as the National Ideology, it was found that 97.8% of students believed that Pancasila was the best ideology for the Indonesian Nation. However, 2.2% of them still do not have awareness in implementing these conscious values of nation and state. That is, most of the students already have the awareness to believe in Pancasila as the national ideology, although it can be seen in the graph below that there are also a small number of them who still do not have this awareness. Even though the percentage is small, this really needs to be watched out for because if there are a number of students who do not believe in Pancasila as the nation's ideology, then there will be a desire to change the nation's ideology at some point in the future, and a small number of these students will be vulnerable to being brainwashed by groups that want a change in the nation's ideology. Thus, it is necessary to periodically socialize, monitor and evaluate to increase student awareness to believe in Pancasila as the best ideology for the Indonesian nation. but this really needs to be watched out for because if there are a number of students who do not believe in Pancasila as the ideology of the nation, then there will be a desire to change the ideology of the nation at some point in the future, and a small number of these students will later be vulnerable to being brainwashed by groups who want a change of ideology nation. Thus, it is necessary to periodically socialize, monitor and evaluate to increase student awareness to believe in Pancasila as the best ideology for the Indonesian nation. but this really needs to be watched out for because if there are a number of students who do not believe in Pancasila as the ideology of the nation, then there will be a desire to change the ideology of the nation at some point in the future, and a small number of these students will later be vulnerable to being brainwashed by groups who want a change of ideology nation. Thus, it is necessary to periodically socialize, monitor and evaluate to increase student awareness to believe in Pancasila as the best ideology for the Indonesian nation.

The embodiment of being willing to sacrifice for the Nation and the State is being willing to sacrifice time, energy, thoughts and property for the public interest so that when the time comes you are ready to sacrifice your body and soul for the interests of the nation and state. Based on the results of the questionnaire regarding the application of the value of Willing to Sacrifice for the nation and the state, it was found that 98.9% of students already had the awareness of being willing to sacrifice for the nation and state, one of which was by wanting to provide help to friends who were experiencing difficulties. However, 1.1% of them still do not have awareness in implementing these values. That is, most of the students already have the awareness to be willing to sacrifice for the nation and state, although it can be seen in the graph below that there are also a small number of them who still do not have this awareness. So, it is necessary to carry out regular socialization, monitoring and evaluation to increase student awareness to be willing to sacrifice for the nation and state.

To increase the initial ability to defend the country can be done through activities that can awaken: Psychologically (mentally) have the characteristics of discipline, tenacity, hard work, obey all applicable laws and regulations, believe in one's own abilities, stand the test, never give up in the face of difficulties to achieve national goals. The initial ability to defend the country is represented by compliance with campus regulations. Based on the results of the questionnaire regarding the application of the value of having initial state defense skills, it was found that 93.3% of students already had initial state defense abilities, one of which was by complying with the regulations that apply on campus. However, 6.7% of them still do not have awareness in implementing these values. That is, most of the students already have the initial ability to defend the country, but it can be seen in the graph below that there are also a small number of them who still do not have this awareness. Thus, it is necessary to carry out regular socialization, monitoring and evaluation to increase student awareness to have the initial ability to defend the country.

Factors that hinder the attitude of defending the country in tertiary institutions, especially in vocational education programs

1. Attitude toward behavior means attitudes toward behavior that are influenced by behavioral beliefs, namely positive or negative evaluations of a particular behavior, reflected in words such as true-wrong, agree-disagree, good-bad. Evaluation of the attitude of defending the country will increase the intention (potential) to defend the country. In measuring how much the attitude factor towards behavior becomes an obstacle to students' defending the country's attitude, a questionnaire instrument was used which was carried out by random sampling method to 178 students majoring in Electrical Engineering, Jakarta State Polytechnic.

3. Subjective norms affect the environment around the individual who expects the individual to behave in a certain way or not. For example religious norms (for religious individuals), social norms, family norms or when people who are important to individuals or tend to be obeyed by individuals consider that loving the motherland as a positive thing, it will increase the intention (potential) to have a high awareness of defending the country .

Based on the results of the questionnaires distributed to students regarding the subjective norms that hindered the implementation of state defense, it was found that 95.5% acknowledged that subjective norms played an important role in influencing the implementation of students' state defense attitude. However, from the results of the questionnaire it was also found that 4.5% of students did not consider this subjective norm to be important. Questions for this factor are made applicable to student activities,

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namely how is student compliance with SOPs in Labs and Workshops. From these results, it can be concluded that the absence of subjective norms also has an important role as one of the inhibiting factors for the implementation of state defense.

3. Behavior control, which is a reference to the difficulty and ease of bringing up a behavior. It has to do with the sources and opportunities to manifest the behavior. For example, the environment around someone who loves their big/easy country will increase individual intentions to grow a high awareness of defending the country.

Based on the results of the questionnaire filled out by students of the Jakarta State Polytechnic Department of Electrical Engineering, it can be seen that 87.2% agree that environmental factors play an important role in students' state defense attitudes. The context of the questions is made close to students in order to facilitate students' understanding of the questions given. Meanwhile, 12.8% of them did not agree that environmental factors played an important role in students' state defense attitudes. This means that environmental factors are also strong factors that hinder the implementation of student state defense.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of this study, it can be concluded that:

- From the results of identifying the challenges in implementing the five values of defending the country in tertiary institutions, especially in students, what is still a big challenge in implementation is the value of love for the motherland and having the initial ability to defend the country.
- Based on the results of the study, of the three inhibiting factors, namely attitude toward belief, subjective norms, control beliefs, it can be concluded that control belief factors, especially environmental factors, are the most dominant inhibiting factors in the implementation of state defense.
- In the implementation of state defense in tertiary institutions, the implementation of non-physical state defense has been accommodated by learning in civics education and Pancasila education courses. However, it is necessary to strengthen physical state defense through activities that can improve students' state defense abilities.

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